

Changes State, Economy, Public Health and Society

(Book of Abstracts)

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Preface

This book includes the abstracts of all the papers presented at the International e-Conference on Changes State, Economy, Public Health and Society, January 16-17, 2022, organized by the Center for Academic & Professional Career Development and Research (CAPCDR). A full conference program can be found before the relevant abstracts.

In accordance with CAPCDR's Publication Policy, the papers presented during this conference will be considered for inclusion in one of CAPCDR's many publications.

The purpose of this abstract book is to provide members of CAPCDR and other academics around the world with a resource through which to discover colleagues and additional research relevant to their own work. This purpose is in congruence with the overall mission of the association. CAPCDR is established in 2021 as an independent academic organization with the mission to become a forum where academics and researchers from all over the world could meet to exchange ideas on their research and consider the future developments of their fields of study.

It is our hope that through CAPCDR conferences and publications, will become a place where academics and researchers from all over the world regularly meet to discuss the developments of their discipline and present their work.

We would like to thank all the participants, the members of the organizing and academic committees, and most importantly the administration staff of CAPCDR for putting this conference and its subsequent publications together. Specific individuals are listed on the following page.

Editorial Board

Welcome Message

It is my great pleasure to welcome you all to our CAPCDR Conference. This is the 2nd conference, the conference is being held online. On behalf of the conference organizers, I would like to thank you all for your participation.

The theme of this conference is "Changes State, Economy, Public Health and Society." More than a year has passed since the outbreak of the pandemic, during which time it has caused enormous loss and damage to people all over the world. Finally, we are beginning to see the light at the end of this dark tunnel as effective vaccines are being rolled out. It is at this juncture that our conference poses the following questions: what will the so-called new normal look like that emerges after the pandemic? and, how are we going to adapt to this new normal? These questions are the central theme of the conference.

In considering the economic perspectives, let me begin by touching on the characteristics of the recession caused by the pandemic and of the following recovery. Simply put, the most important feature of both the recession and the recovery is their unevenness. Each recession is different, but this time, the difference in the severity of the downturn among industries, business types, and occupations has been particularly dramatic. People have changed their behavior under the pandemic and in response to the containment measures. Demand for goods and services that require in-person contact has plummeted. These industries have taken a huge hit and their recovery has been slow

The unevenness of the recession and the ongoing recovery could reinforce three trends that have continued since around the global financial crisis of the late 2000s. The first trend is an increase in saving. Against the backdrop of uncertainty over the course of the pandemic and recovery, saving has increased substantially. The second trend is an increase in economic inequality. The impact of the pandemic appears to be uneven and regressive, as the negative impact has been more tilted toward low-income earners and young workers. There are therefore concerns over an increase in income and wealth inequality. The third trend is an increase in debt. Be it public or private, borrowing is essential to smooth economic activity and to mitigate the negative impact of the pandemic. As a result of the necessary response to tackle the pandemic, debt has been mounting in many countries.

Besides these trends, another important area to consider when we look at the post-pandemic economy is the underlying structural changes emerging in technology and industry and the accompanying changes in the behavior of households and firms. Perhaps the most important change we have seen during the health crisis is the wide and rapid spread of digitalization. Many areas of the economy have been affected by the shift from in-person to online activities. While the movement of people across national borders has almost completely stopped, digital technology has removed geographical restrictions and eased the potential economic downturn caused by the health crisis. New businesses that use digital technology have been emerging in a wide range of areas.

Looking ahead, the important point is whether these structural changes lead to a wide-spread increase in productivity in the economy, and whether the fruits of growth are widely shared throughout the society. Advances in digitalization are expected to enhance productivity and benefit a wide range of individuals and firms by promoting innovation and efficient resource allocation. On the other hand, it is necessary to pay attention to the possibility that, if the fruits of growth are concentrated in a small fraction of society and inequality increases, it may be difficult to achieve inclusive economic growth.

Looking to the future, the challenges facing policymakers will likely change. The initial phase has been liquidity support. This will likely change to solvency and corporate viability problems, and then to resource re-allocation in response to structural changes in the economy. At the same time, policymakers face the additional challenges of the economic inequality that has become even more apparent during this health crisis, and the response to increasing worldwide concerns over climate change. Likewise, the nature of the policy responses will also shift

from temporary first aid measures to medium- to long-term structural policies. To one degree or another, this set of challenges is related to the stability of inflation, the real economy, and the financial system.

So far, I have touched on the economic perspectives and on policy challenges. These factors will in part shape the post-pandemic new normal, although exactly how remains to be seen. One thing for certain, however, is that the world we live in will not be the same as that before the pandemic.

After more than a year of living with the pandemic, we have seen a drastic change in the way our society works. In particular, the expansion of digital technology has led to a fundamental transformation in society, in ways that we could not have imagined. As I noted earlier, the shift from in-person to online activities has taken place in all aspects, such as of work, business, education, and health. Expansion in the areas of remote working, online shopping, remote learning, and telemedicine is just a few examples. I have benefited considerably from digital technology that allows me to reach people in different places all over the world, all at the same time. Indeed, it is thanks to the online format of this conference that I am able to welcome you all together today.

Of course, there are two sides to any new technology, both positive and negative, and we cannot ignore the importance of the kind of exchange that can only come through face-to-face communication. In that respect, I do feel a certain ambivalence toward digital technology. And yet, even after we have overcome the pandemic, a full return to the less digital pre-pandemic world seems unlikely. Society has undergone irreversible change as it has adapted to the pandemic by expanding and accelerating digitalization. By building on our discoveries and experience during this health crisis, we should forge ahead and shape the new society and economy -- the new normal.

Over the past 15 years, we have been through two global crises: the financial crisis and the health crisis. In the current crisis, academic disciplines, including economics, have made a significant contribution.

We are beginning to see the light at the end of this pandemic tunnel, but the light does not clearly reveal the shape of the society and economy we are approaching. Therefore, the theme of our conference, "Changes State, Economy, Public Health and Society," is going to cover a wide range of issues. Given the considerable uncertainty we face, it is only natural that we will have different views on the relative importance of the issues involved and the direction our discussions should take. Although we have only a few hours today and tomorrow, it is very encouraging to be able to welcome representatives from various institutions and from academia to participate in these discussions. I look forward to hearing a broad spectrum of views and insights into the post-pandemic economy and policies.

Thank you.

Professor Dr Kazi Abdul Mannan
Chairperson.
Conference Organizing Committee

About CACPDR

Center for Academic & Professional Career Development and Research (CAPCDR) is a consortium of research and policy makers drawn from national and international universities, institutes and organizations. CAPCDR is presently based in Asia and is shaping as the largest such group focusing specifically on the issues related to academic career, professional development and research.

The CAPCDR works as an academic and policy think tank by engaging national and international experts from academics, practitioners and policy makers in a broad range of research areas. In the changing global environment of academic research and policy making, the role of CAPCDR will be of immense help to the various stakeholders. Many developing countries cannot afford to miss the opportunity to harness the knowledge revolution of the present era.

Dr Khandaker Mursheda Farhana

Director
CAPCDR

About Conference

Dear All,

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a dramatic loss of human life worldwide and presents an unprecedented challenge to public health, formal education, technical and vocational education, finance, supply chain, food systems and the world of work. The economic and social disruption caused by the pandemic is devastating: tens of millions of people are at risk of falling into extreme poverty, while the number of undernourished people, currently estimated at nearly 690 million, could increase by up to 132 million by the end of the year 2020.

Nearly half of the world's 3.3 billion global workforce are at risk of losing their livelihoods. Informal economy workers are particularly vulnerable because the majority lack social protection and access to quality health care and have lost access to productive assets. During lockdowns, many are unable to feed themselves and their families.

Dear Participants,

The pandemic has been affecting the entire food system and has laid bare its fragility. Border closures, trade restrictions and confinement measures have been disrupting domestic and international food supply chains and reducing access to healthy, safe and diverse diets. The pandemic has decimated jobs and placed millions of livelihoods at risk. As breadwinners lose jobs, fall ill and die, the food security and nutrition of millions of women and men are under threat.

Millions of agricultural workers – waged and self-employed – while feeding the world, regularly face high levels of working poverty, malnutrition and poor health, and suffer from a lack of safety and labour protection as well as other types of abuse. When experiencing income losses, they may resort to negative coping strategies, such as distress sale of assets, predatory loans or child labour. Migrant agricultural workers are particularly vulnerable, because they face risks in their transport, working and living conditions and struggle to access support measures put in place by governments. Guaranteeing the safety and health of all agri-food workers – from primary producers to those involved in food processing, transport and retail, including street food vendors – as well as better incomes and protection, will be critical to saving lives and protecting public health, people's livelihoods and food security.

In the COVID-19 crisis food security, public health, and employment and labour issues, in particular workers' health and safety, converge. Adhering to workplace safety and health practices and ensuring access to decent work and the protection of labour rights in all industries will be crucial in addressing the human dimension of the crisis. Immediate and purposeful action to save lives and livelihoods should include extending social protection towards universal health coverage and income support for those most affected. These include workers in the informal economy and in poorly protected and low-paid jobs, including youth, older workers, and migrants. Particular attention must be paid to the situation of women, who are over-represented in low-paid jobs and care roles.

Dear Participants,

COVID19 has disrupted the whole business world, Supply chain, especially education and tourism. As per <https://unctad.org/news/> Global economy could lose over \$4 trillion due to COVID-19 impact on tourism

Countries dealing with existing humanitarian crises or emergencies are particularly exposed to the effects of COVID-19. Responding swiftly to the pandemic, while ensuring that humanitarian and recovery assistance reaches those most in need, is critical.

Now is the time for global solidarity and support, especially with the most vulnerable in our societies, particularly in the emerging and developing world. Only together can we overcome the intertwined health and social and economic impacts of the pandemic and prevent its escalation into a protracted humanitarian and food security catastrophe, with the potential loss of already achieved development gains.

The global development organizations need to develop long-term sustainable strategies to address the challenges facing each sector and to support counties in their crisis response measures and efforts to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

We must rethink the future of our environment and tackle climate change and environmental degradation with ambition and urgency. Only then can we protect the health, livelihoods, food security and nutrition of all people, and ensure that our 'new normal' is a better one.

Dear Listeners and participants,

As such COVID19 has given us a new pandemic experience which we did not face recent past, it is imperative for research in each sector affected by COVID19. It is needed to share the research findings among the world scholars, the industrial stake holders and policy makers of countries, regional policy making bodies and world policy advising bodies.

COVID19 is not a country issue, not a regional issue rather it is a global issue and total world should move comprehensively and completely. So the knowledge sharing regarding the pandemic must be of cross border to build a better back.

For sharing such on field research findings on COVID 19 Pandemic impacts, CACPDR is organizing this very timely international e-Conference. And it is very important and a matter of pleasure that 54 Papers will be presented from 15 countries research scholars where many more showed their interest to participate but for time constraint we are unable to accommodate.

Hope this conference will give inputs to the policy makers for a better come back policy formulation and make a foot print for other scholars for future research.

Hope you all will enjoy the sessions and the conference.

Thank you, JajakAllah

G M Omar Faruque Chowdhury
Secretary General
Conference Organizing Committee

Afghanistan's Trade Challenges with Central Asian Countries (Case Study of Marble Exports)

Faryal Dehqan

(Scientific supervisor - ass. Tikhomirov Anton Fedorovich)

Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University

Abstract

The Taliban government faces an imminent threat to Afghanistan; the war-torn banking system is collapsing. This has deprived many people of this country of access to crypto currency. Banks in Afghanistan, sometime after the Taliban ordered the reopening of banks and other service has issued, etc. were opened, but the limits to their disposition has been, for instance, any merchant can only weeks 50 thousand Afghani from the bank account of their cash, and that this impact is very bad for the traders present in Afghanistan, for example, that all the money on their bank accounts, their existing industry, and from them they can't use. In this article, a business model was developed that, in the analysis of the subject I see that the forecast value of the next of a series using the method of time series is of special importance for many studies. In economic and financial issues, forecasting indices and prices is of particular importance. So far, conventional time series models have been used to model financial and economic series, which were not so convenient. Because in the Financial series instability strongly depends on its past and must be considered in modelling. Models that examine this topic and check the volatility of the model are called Arc models. The price of marble in Afghanistan is lower than in the countries of the region, but the challenges in Afghanistan are not properly exported to the marble of Central Asia. There are main challenges when the absence of specialists in mining, the lack of security for mining and export, the lack of price stability and the impact of prices. To solve this business, there are a few solutions that this Afghanistan provides several experts in this sector to create a study on the security and export management of the state market.